

This was identified as sucrose; octaacetate, m.p. 68-70°.

Wet methanol eluted a solid (850 mg) identified as sodium chloride.

Isolation of D-mannitol: *Adenia cissampeloides* stem collected in April from Ojoo, was crushed and sun-dried for 4 days. The dry plant material (4.5 kg) was soxhlet-extracted with ethanol for 26 h. The ethanol concentrate was extracted several times with chloroform leaving a residual thick syrup which on standing overnight gave some solids, recrystallised from ethanol as white crystals (13.8 g), m.p. 167-69.5°, identified as D-mannitol¹.

D-Mannitol (19 mg) was acetylated in the usual way using pyridine and acetic anhydride to give the hexaacetate (32 mg) which crystallised as white plates from ethanol, m.p. 122-124°. Benzoylation of the D-mannitol (45 mg) in the usual way using benzoyl chloride and pyridine afforded the hexabenzoate as white needles from methanol (171 mg), m.p. 154-156°.

D-Mannitol (290 mg) was suspended in dry and redistilled acetone (20 cm³). Concentrated H₂SO₄ (2 drops) was added and the mixture stirred at room temperature for 3 days. Sodium bicarbonate was added until the mixture became basic to litmus paper. Water (40 cm³) was added and the mixture extracted with ether (4 × 100 cm³). The combined ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled to give D-mannitol tri-*O*-isopropylidene as large white needles, m.p. 67-69°.

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Biflavonoid from the Family Salicaceae

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THE genus *Salix*¹ (Fam.: Salicaceae) comprising about 300 species, is distributed throughout the northern hemisphere with a few into the southern hemisphere. *Salix alba* Linn.² (Sub. sp.: *S. coerulea*, known as cricket bat willow) owes its importance both from economic and medicinal points of view. Medicinally, it is used in haemoptysis, acute rheumatism, gout fever, diarrhoea and dysentery. *S. alba* and *S. fragilis* leaves (procured from Manali, Himachal Pradesh) were examined for their biflavonoid contents and found to contain two apigenin dimers with linkages [I-3', II-8] (1) and [I-8, II-8] (2) alongwith apigenin. The presence of

biflavones is being reported for the first time in Salicaceae family and their occurrence in *Salix* species may serve as a useful taxonomic marker.

Experimental

Dried and powdered leaves of *Salix alba* (2.5 kg) after treatment with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and benzene were exhaustively extracted with acetone. The dark viscous mass obtained on concentration was successively digested with petroleum ether, benzene, chloroform and water. The residue was refluxed with ethyl acetate for 48 h, then filtered and filtrate evaporated to give a dark brown solid. It was chromatographed on Si-gel using organic solvents in increasing order of polarity. The flavonoid³ fraction obtained from C₆H₆-EtOAc (7:3) eluates gave an elongated spot on tlc (methylated product exhibited two distinct spots) and this on further chromatography (Si-gel, C₆H₆-EtOAc-AcOH=8:5:2) yielded compounds A and B. The fraction eluted with C₆H₆-EtOAc (8:2) afforded compound C.

Compound A: It was crystallised from MeOH as yellow cubes (300 mg), m.p. 320°, R_f 0.18 (Si-gel G, benzene-pyridine-formic acid (BPF)=36:9:5), M⁺ 538 (C₃₀H₁₈O₁₀); λ_{max} (EtOH) 272 and 335 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3400 (OH) and 1635 cm⁻¹ (flavone CO). Methylation with Me₂SO₄-K₂CO₃ in dry acetone and crystallisation (CHCl₃-MeOH) afforded a methyl ether as colourless needles, m.p. 174°, R_f 0.40 (Si-gel G, BPF=36:9:5), M⁺ 622 (C₃₆H₃₀O₁₀). R_f, m.p. and shade in uv light indicated it to be amentoflavone hexamethyl ether^{4,5}. On acetylation with Ac₂O-Py it gave an acetate, colourless needles from CHCl₃-MeOH, m.p. 237°. Pmr spectral data of the methyl ether and acetate were found identical with those of hexamethyl ether and hexaacetate of amentoflavone^{5,6}. The compound was, therefore, characterised as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7 hexahydroxy [I-3, II-8] biflavone (amentoflavone) (1).

Compound B: Yellow cubes (MeOH) (190 mg), m.p. 358°, R_f 0.18 (Si-gel G, BPF=36:9:5), M^+ 538 ($C_{30}H_{10}O_{10}$); λ_{max} (EtOH) 274 and 333 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3380 (OH) and 1630 cm^{-1} (flavone CO). The methyl ether (Me_2SO_4/K_2CO_3), colourless prisms ($CHCl_3$ -MeOH), m.p. 298°, R_f 0.43 (Si-gel G, BPF=36:9:5), M^+ 622 ($C_{30}H_{30}O_{10}$) was found identical in R_f , m.p. and fluorescence in uv light with cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether⁴. Acetylation (Ac_2O -Py) provided a hexaacetate as colourless needles ($CHCl_3$ -MeOH), m.p. 249°. Pmr spectral data of these derivatives were found comparable with those of hexamethyl ether and hexaacetate of cupressuflavone⁷. The compound was thus identified as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7 hexahydroxy[I-8, II-8]biflavone (cupressuflavone) (2).

Compound C: Yellow cubes (MeOH) (160 mg), m.p. 348°, R_f 0.52 (Si-gel G, BPF=36:9:5), M^+ 270 ($C_{15}H_{10}O_5$); λ_{max} (EtOH) 269 and 341 nm. Methyl ether, R_f 0.54 (Si-gel G, BPF=36:9:5) was found identical in R_f and shade in uv light with apigenin trimethyl ether⁴. Acetylation (Ac_2O -Py) provided colourless cubes ($CHCl_3$ -MeOH), m.p. 193°, pmr ($CDCl_3$) spectral data and m.p. of which were found comparable with apigenin triacetate⁸. The compound was thus identified as apigenin.

Acetone extract of air-dried and powdered leaves of *Salix fragilis* (1.5 kg) after usual purification by

solvent fractionation and column chromatography was separated into amentoflavone (1) (180 mg), cupressuflavone (2) (120 mg) and apigenin by preparative tlc and further Si-gel column. These compounds were identified by direct comparison (R_f , m.p., m.m.p and shade in uv light) with authentic samples of themselves and their derivatives.

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